

A BRIEF EXAMINATION OF AN AUTISTIC MIND: FROM MINDSIGHT TO MINDBLINDNESS, FROM MINDFULNESS TO MINDLESSNESS

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Autism or Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in full was first coined in 1911 by Dr Eugen Bleuler, a Swiss psychiatrist, who had been working with schizophrenic patients, whom he noted to be socially and emotionally isolated and extremely self-absorbed. However, our understanding of ASD comes from the early writings of Dr Leo Kanner and Dr Hans Asperger – both have been honoured as the pioneers in the ASD field. Dr Kanner published his paper on autism in 1943 and his definition of autism was then known as early infantile or childhood autism displaying a triad of impairments in social interaction, communication and imagination. Dr Asperger's paper published in 1944 has provided a description of children with similar autistic traits except that his subjects were of higher IQs and precocious language skills (i.e., hyperlexic tendency). Both psychiatrists described symptoms of two different sub-groups among a wide range of disorders affecting social interaction and communication. In between them, there are various subtypes of autism and related anomalies whose causes remain very much unknown although research studies are currently being done in the following areas: brain, genetics and epigenetics, environmental factors, immune and gastrointestinal systems, immunization, and pregnancy and perinatal anoxia (see Exkorn, 2005).

Many, if not all, formal definitions of ASD have chosen to focus on autistic deficits and not on their strengths. A common emphasis is on empathizing deficits, which refer to one's failure to make connection to another individual's experience and to respond appropriately to that person. This has been termed as mindblindness – a cognitive disorder in which one is unable to attribute mental states to oneself and other selves. As a result of this disorder, the person is not unaware or mindful of others' mental states (Frith, 2001). Moreover, the person is incapable of attributing beliefs and desires to others (Gallagher & Frith, 2003). The capability to develop a mental awareness (or mindsight) of what is in someone's mind is known as the Theory of Mind (ToM), which allows one to attribute one's behavior and actions to various mental states of mind (see Chia, in the Fall 2007 issue of Unlimited Human! for more detail). Mindblindness – a total opposite of mindsight – has been associated with patients with ASD and schizophrenia as these individuals

tend to show deficits in social insight. In addition, recent research on ToM and mindblindness has been extended to include other disorders such as dementia, bipolar personality disorders, and anti-social personality disorders as well as problems related to the normal process of aging (Brune, 2005).

However, recent studies (e.g., Baron-Cohen et al., 2003; Lawson, Baron-Cohen, & Wheelwright, 2004; Myers, Baron-Cohen, & Wheelwright, 2004) suggest that individuals with ASD have intact or even superior systemizing ability, i.e., the ability to analyze and build systems so as to understand and predict the functional behavior of impersonal events or inanimate or abstract entities.

As a result, Chia (2012) has argued for the need to re-define and expand the term autism spectrum disorder (ASD) as a neuro-developmental syndrome of constitutional origin (genetic) and whose cause could also be epigenetic, and its onset is usually around first three years of birth, with empathizing or mentalizing deficits that result in a triad of impairments in communication, social interaction, and imagination, with manifestation of repetitive stereotyped behaviors, but may, on the other hand, display (especially by autistic savants) or hide (especially by autistic crypto-savants) a strong systemizing drive that accounts for a distinct triad of strengths in good attention to detail, deep narrow interests, and islets of ability.

Autism as it is understood now

The latest fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-V) published by the American Psychiatric Association (APA, 2013) provides a good starting point for all to understand what the disorder is like. Pervasive Developmental Disorders (PDD) is used as a collective term to include autistic disorder (i.e., the classical autism as described by Dr Leo Kanner) and the non-autistic PDD, which includes Asperger's Syndrome, Fragile-X Syndrome, Rett's Syndrome, Childhood Disintegrative Disorder and PDD-Not Otherwise Specified (PDD-NOS). Table 1 shows some changes in the DSM diagnostic criteria for ASD over a period of time from 1980 to 2013 with the publication of DSM-V. Asperger's Syndrome has been dropped from this latest edition.

Table 1. Changes in the DSM diagnostic criteria for ASD 1980-2013

DSM Editions	DSM-III (1980)	DSM-III-R (1987)	DSM-IV (1994) DSM-IV-TR (2000)	DSM-V (2013)
Onset of ASD	Onset before 30 months	Onset before 36 months	Delays or abnormal functioning in one area (social interaction, language or play) before 36 months	Symptoms in early developmental period (may not manifest until social demands exceed limited capacities)
Qualitative impairment	Gross deficits in language development and a pervasive lack of responsiveness to others.	Qualitative impairment in both verbal and nonverbal communication as well as in reciprocal social interaction.	Qualitative impairment in communication and social interaction.	Persistent deficits in social interaction and communication as well as deficits in social-emotional reciprocity and social relationships.

Theory of Mind

As mentioned earlier, the Theory of Mind (ToM) refers to the ability to attribute mental states of mind, such as beliefs, desires, intents, knowledge, pretensions, and list can go on, to oneself and other selves with an understanding that other selves have their own beliefs, desires and intents that can be different from one’s own (Premack & Woodruff, 1978). Baron-Cohen (2001) describes ToM as being able to infer the full range of mental states (beliefs, desires, intentions, imagination, emotions, etc.) that cause action.

In brief, having a ToM is to be able to reflect on the contents of one’s own and other’s minds. People with attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), ASD, schizophrenia and substance abuse (e.g., alcohol abuse) often show a lack of ToM or having a faulty ToM which, in other words, is termed as mindblindness, creating major barriers to communication and socio-spatial closeness. Such barriers cause those, who are closest to the mindblind individual, a sense of, be it real or perceived, lacking in empathy from that individual.

The Four Sensory Levels

According to Siegel (2007), there are eight senses, which we have re-categorized under four sensory levels (see Figure 1) as follows:

First sensory level. This level consists of five exteroceptive senses ((visual/sight, auditory/hearing, haptic/touch, olfactory/smell and gustatory/taste) that “bring in information from the outside world, enabling us to sense this physical domain of reality” (Siegel, 2007, p.122).

Second sensory level. This level refers to the sixth sense – also known as interoceptive sensation – includes the sensations we experience in our arms and legs as well as the movements associated with the limbs, the muscular tension or relaxation, “the state of our internal milieu, including our organs ... We use the process of interoception to perceive these important sixth sense inputs, bringing them into our sensorimotor awareness” (Siegel, 2007, p.122).

Figure 1. Four Sensory Levels

Third sensory level. According to Siegel (2007), this seventh sense enables aspects of mind (i.e., thoughts, feelings, intentions, attitudes, concepts, images, beliefs, hopes, dreams) of oneself or other selves to be brought into the focus of attention. This sensory ability to perceive the mind is known as mindsight and enables one to gain deep insight and empathy.

Mindsight also refers to mindful awareness that contains the meta-cognitive processes enabling both awareness of awareness and the focus of attention on the nature of the mind itself. Hence, these reflective practices directly develop one’s mindsight abilities. The opposite of mindsight is mindblindness, which we have described briefly earlier as the inability to attribute mental states to oneself and other selves. Hence, one may not be aware or mindful of others’ mental states (Frith, 2001; Gallagher & Frith, 2003).

Fourth sensory level. This is the highest level of our sensory awareness in terms of our sense of the mind which represents our sense of relationship and connection with some being around us within a bio-ecological system. This sense of being (which can be a small part of an even larger “living” whole that we called Mother Nature) and belongingness (as in the case of our dwelling on this planet Earth as

earthlings together with other living and non-living things) involves human relationships, prayer and meditation as well as, for example, some form of social and/or academic fellowship might enable people to feel that they belong and have established membership with others. In other words, we attune with other people and are aware of feelings felt by others and this enables us to feel a part of the larger whole or community. Siegel (2007) has termed it as relational sense. Previously, this eighth sense was known as sense ability (Helmering, 1999).

In the highly acclaimed 2009's American epic science fiction action movie *Avatar* (written and directed by James Cameron), this eighth sense can be best illustrated and demonstrated by the blue-skinned sapient humanoids of the Na'vi tribe who live in harmony with nature and worship a mother goddess called Eywa found in a giant arboreal called Hometree, which is their biological neural network native to their planet Pandora.

Mindfulness to Mindlessness

Mindfulness (also known as mindful awareness) is a psychological concept that focuses on attention and awareness. To the Buddhists, mindfulness is a spiritual or psychological faculty that is considered to be of great importance in the path to enlightenment. Although its beginning is based on the concept of mindfulness in Buddhist meditation, today mindfulness is often taught independently of religion. It is popularized in the West by Dr Jon Kabat-Zinn (see Kabat-Zinn, 2005, for more detail), the founding Executive Director of the Center for Mindfulness in Medicine, Health Care, and Society at the University of Massachusetts Medical School.

In its general sense, mindfulness concerns two important things: first, it is waking up from a mundane life of automaticity; and second, it is being sensitive to novelty in our daily experiences. Being mindfully aware involves more than just being aware; "it involves being aware of aspects of the mind itself" (Siegel, 2007, p.5). Chia and Kee (2010) have coined the term *awarizing* – an active form of rather than just being aware – that refers to the same thing, too. In other words, mindfulness awakens us and empowers us to reflect, make choices and thus change becomes possible.

However, mindfulness can turn into a senseless mind or what Langer (1989) has termed as mindlessness. For example, someone by the name John goes about doing his daily chores such as waking up at 7am, brushing his teeth, changing up his nightgown, eating his usual breakfast while reading his daily newspaper ... without much thinking involved, soon he becomes an automaton. It becomes ritualistic or a routine. Suppose something unexpected happens, the alarm clock fails to ring or even more drastic, a super-typhoon comes tearing ferociously across the country destroying everything on its pathway, John will in a mindless state of not knowing what to do or is still trying to make sense out of what is happening around him. Before he can realize what is

going on, it would be too late for him to react or respond to the situation. Together with his house and everything else, he will be blown away or destroyed.

As in the case of a person with an autistic mind, he keeps repeating a certain task over and over again or feels secured when sticking to his normal routine (e.g., taking the same route to work). Although the person becomes better at the task or gets to his workplace in the shortest possible time, it will soon come to a point when he assumes he could do the task although he no longer knows how he does it. Repetition creates mindlessness with some sort of "[A] familiar structure or rhythm that helps lead to mental laziness, acting as a signal that there is no need to pay attention" (Langer, 1989, p.21). In fact, questioning or interrupting the process may yield some surprising results. As in this case, the person with an autistic mind performs the task so expertly or mindlessly that he may no longer be consciously aware or able to explain the process.

Proposed Model of Autism

From a mind-based perspective, a person with an autistic mind should be viewed as someone, whose ToM has stronger mindblindness and deeper mindlessness rather than having a faulty ToM. As shown in Figure 2 below, the symbol of a black circle represents the mind of a person with Asperger's Syndrome (although this condition is no longer used in the DSM-V) who is slightly more mindful of his surrounding though still in the domain of mindblindness (due to his poor communication and social interaction skills). However, the symbol of a black star represents a typical autistic mind (or a person with Autistic Disorder) that is both strongly mindblind and deeply mindless.

Figure 2. Proposed Mind-based Model of Autism

This model that we have proposed here does not offer a solution to eradicate the condition of ASD but provides another angle of looking at the condition. It serves to remind us that instead of looking at people with ASD as having a faulty ToM, we may want to take a different viewpoint from the conventional one, i.e., to look at these people and see them as having very poor mindsight and extremely weak mindfulness. Perhaps what needs to be done next is to calibrate the axis between Mindsight and Mindblindness as well as the axis between Mindfulness and Mindlessness in order

to make it into a useful measure. This is beyond the scope of our current article. Further studies are urgently in need to find out how we can help to shift an autistic mind gradually from mindblindness to mindsight, from mindlessness to mindfulness. Perhaps it would be good to begin working with those with mild ASD.

As a follow-up action to this article, we would explore the possibility of carrying out an investigative study with the help of a qualified mindfulness practitioner to find out the effectiveness of mindfulness as therapy with its principles and practice applied in helping people with ASD. We hope to report our findings in the near future in *Unlimited Human!*

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